

THEORETICAL BASIS OF ASSESSMENT OF STANDARDS AND STYLE IN CONFLICT TEXTS IN LINGUISTIC EXPERTISE

Yakubova Sevara

Tashkent state pedagogy university

Uzbek language and him teaching methodology department. PhD

Email : s.yoqubova@bk.ru , phone : 90.915-55-01

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11532471>

ANNOTATSIYA

Lingvistik ekspertizada konfliktli matn muhim tadqiq obyekti sanaladi. Muallifni aniqlashga qaratilgan lingvistik ekspertizalarda, asosan, adabiy me'yor va me'yordan chekinish hollari identifikatsiyalash jarayoida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Bunda adabiy me'yorga muvofiq hamda adaviy me'yordan chekinish hollari qo'lyozma va bosma matnlarda alohida tahlil qilinishi lozim. Maqolada lingvistik ekspertizada me'yor tushunchasi, noadabiy unsurlar hamda matnning uslubiy xoslanishini baholash singari masalalarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvistik ekspertiza, me'yor, noadabiy unsur, anonimlik, identifikatsiyalash, atributlar, norma, talab.

Аннотация

В лингвистической экспертизе конфликтный текст является важным объектом исследования. В лингвистических исследованиях, направленных на идентификацию автора, случаи литературной нормы и отступления от нормы в основном становятся важными в процессе идентификации. При этом в соответствии с литературной нормой и отдельно в рукописных и печатных текстах должны быть проанализированы случаи отступления от литературной нормы. В статье особое внимание уделяется таким вопросам, как понятие нормы в лингвистической экспертизе, нелитературные элементы, а также оценка стилистической специфики текста. **Ключевые слова:** лингвистическая экспертиза, норма, нелитературный элемент, анонимность, идентификация, атрибуция, норма, требование.

ANNOTATION

Conflict text is considered an important research object in linguistic expertise. In the linguistic examinations aimed at identifying the author, mainly cases of literary norms and deviations from norms are important in the process of identification. In this case, it is necessary to analyze separately the cases of departure from the literary norm and the literary norm in manuscript and printed texts. The article focuses on issues such as the concept of norms, non-literary elements and assessment of the stylistic features of the text in linguistic expertise.

Key words: linguistic expertise, norm, non-literary element, anonymity, identification, attributes, norm, demand.

INTRODUCTION.

As you know , *the norm* and *style* each other requirement which concepts is considered Literary language standards scientific in terms of deep study , it scientific and theoretical in

terms of justification and with him depends problems the solution to find of linguistics practical linguistics field in front of the most current from issues one is considered Literary of the tongue to himself special aspects of it development laws , in it language of units speech to the situation suitable without application opportunities research without doing practical linguistics issues in particular justified conclusion release possible it's not . " Language , speech normal the fact that clearly But that's it norms set , their correctness , acceptability determination , evaluation easy the work it's not . Because for now until languages , including Uzbek of the language norms , purpose compliance , each speech situation , situation , speech style requirements point of view from the point of view right not coming enough respectively studied it's not . This issue study , own in turn , language norm theory , linguistic the norm about doctrine with is connected . Such doctrine there is . But for now until language norm the concept of it understanding , interpretation to do , concrete the norm designation and of assessment many sides scientific in terms of controversial or is unclear . In this respect norms , including literary the norm about present period in linguistics there is has been thoughts analysis to do and known conclusions release Uzbek of linguistics linguistically the norm theory to develop service to do no doubt " [1; 9-10 pp.].

Books review

In linguistics norm to the concept relatively example , example , norm , rule such as different terms being used although they are content is the only goal on the way service does This is the case to linguistics about in dictionaries being given see also in the definitions thrown away There is thoughts based on the norm essence as follows describe possible : one on the other hand , this known communicative to the task and known linguistic-speech to the situation according to speaker or the writer for normal options error free choose own opportunity giver rule , skill , qualification , mechanism if , the second on the other hand , that speaker or the writer concrete speech in communication to use for choose received language tools , that is done app done are opportunities " [p. 7; 39]. Literary language relentlessly in progress as , speech to culture dedicated each in the work literary language standards problem as the main issue is considered . Them right as noted , " Language norm big social important have It is in the language always happen being standing to changes endure giving it from distortions preserves generations between communication , different periods cultural speech traditions consistency provides " [10; pp. 47-74]. Literary language norm , his essence , literary language development depends without changed standing , development laws in what manifestation it will be questions past of the century second in half main issues as day order placed was [6; p. 27]

SIOjegov by as stated : "... norm this social in progress together there is was , there is was , new appear has been or of the past less used language to select elements (lexical , pronunciation , morphological , syntactic). result as formed , to society service who does useful (correct , acceptable) language tools is a sum , broad in a sense this elements is an assessment " [8]. In society wide public national of culture all treasures , that's it including literary the language mastering at the time speech culture issues the first level important have will be Social of life new structure oral of communication new of forms development , public , social of speech for example not seen development help will give . Public activities , press , literature , radio, television , voice movies wide of the public property turned . So so , of the speech communication tool as exemplary , correct , clear and expressive to be , then to

communicate interrupt giving and the language impoverishing units not to be aspiration very important [9; 285-291b.].

In this regard the following thoughts are also considered owner : " Standard this language units mutually good to understand necessity because of from him which uses people by created , language of appearance in practice has been is a feature . That 's exactly it necessity language system to unity reach on the way to people any option ok see , from another give up passing away desire gives birth Such is the society to unity reach on the way aspiration with together language norm national literary in the language high to the degree rising and strengthening goes " [3; 234-235b.].

Content

General the norm known made , for example , Uzbek of the language all in appearances being used norms of the system from the total consists of Private norm - general of the norm speech appearances , forms , language in forms sure are appearances . Uzbek of the language the following private norms about to speak can :

1. Uzbek literary language norm ;
2. Uzbek dialect and dialects norm (dialectal norm);
3. Uzbek conversation speech norm ;
4. Uzbek of the language social networks , i.e. " social dialects " , " social " slang " norm (slang, professional speech views of argon another to different special norms)" [2; 19-p].

Today in the day Uzbek literary of the language somewhat processed , known level to the mold put standards as follows is displayed :

- lexical-semantic norm - lexicon (word application) norm ;
- standard of pronunciation (orphoepic) ;
- accentological (word and in forms accent correctness) standard ;
- phonetic standard ;
- grammatical (morphological and syntactic) standard ;
- word to make standard ;
- spelling standard ;
- writing (graphics) standard ;
- punctuation standard ;
- methodical norm [5; p. 39].

Literary from the norm estrangement phonetic , lexical , grammatical , stylistic in terms of done increase can Literary from the norm retreat as a result rude phonetic , lexical , grammatical units surface will come . In particular , the color indicator *ink* lexicon unit literary to the norm according to , however his dialectal option - *lock* or foreign in the language translation - *fioletivy* from the norm outside Or - *of* , - *of* agreement of forms the same that's it in the form or - *in* abbreviation in the form application literary the norm if counted , - *of* in place - *ni* , - *ni* instead of -*ti* , -*di* of additions application rude of units surface to come reason will be

Linguistic in expertise rude units base create them in practice apply important importance occupation is enough That's why anonymity with depends cases written text of the author identification in determining directly rude lexicon elements important importance occupation is enough Usually people daily in communication age , gender , specific to the area feature the point in terms of common and special lexicon from the base they use Separately characteristic expressive units during rude units main place holds Text authorization in the

matter of rude units study , analysis to do and in practice apply text authorship in the installation important factor being service does

Linguistic in expertise text authorization wide comprehensive concept is counted . In this " Text the author how determination necessary ?" , " The author determination attributes from what consists of ?" like to questions clarity input a linguist is an expert in charge of tasks in turn enters In the text of words application frequency , age , area, social affiliation , gender identity according to signs determination for of the text linguistic features carefully will be checked . Malcolm Coulthard has done significant work on identifying the author of a conflicting text in world linguistic expertise [4; p. 250].

Results

The above-mentioned research is generally based on the attributes of identifying the author of various written texts. In Uzbek linguistics, a number of studies have been made about the lexical-semantic types and forms of expression of non-literary elements. However, from the point of view of linguistic expertise, the amount of research on the characterization of non-literary elements according to age characteristics is insufficient. The following aspects are emphasized in the researches carried out on Uzbek linguistic expertise:

Recently, as a result of the increase in messages and comments affecting the social security, honor and dignity of a person, attracting the attention of the general public, the number of lawsuits in this regard is increasing. Especially as a result of the development of the Internet, the increase in the number of political messages that attack the constitutional system, incite national, ethnic, racial and religious conflicts , promote war, and increase the number of cybercrimes is due to the improvement of criminalistics, as well as qualified linguists-experts. causes the need to increase. Experts who initially worked with manuscript texts now had to work with a wide range of conflicting texts.

Summary

In the analysis of manuscript texts, experts emphasize the aspects of personality psychology, personality, mental, graphology, belief systems, graphotherapy, and nervous pathways. Therefore, various studies have been carried out by scientists regarding the direct influence of these factors on writing. In most countries outside the United States, the term graphology is actively used when examining texts related to handwriting. However, the main purpose of graphology is to determine aspects of human character based on writing. France , Europe , India and whole in the world hand writing analysis one in the field combined . It 's like you without a doctor the conclusion only one his hand in the inscription to forms looking to say looks like In this field different fields and different methodologies there is . In particular , Gestalt method of the early 1900s german to research based on and Rorschach's ink spots to the tests looks like Roschach Gestalt therapist as initially whole manuscript seeing comes out , then the subject parts to separate started His in his opinion , the whole his parts from the total is greater [11; p. 15]. These feelings own into take many personal features seeing exit own undertake takes Gestalt therapist , in fact , very wide the point from the point of view works Manuscripts analysis in doing characteristic stroke method now the most famous is considered This is the method especially in the 1950s books written by Milton Bunker basis put in He was in Chicago from the 1950s to the mid -90s until very famous was study to the company basis put Bunker arm writing analysis to do for this the approach From France to America take came expert was This is the method each in the manuscript the blow considers

it important and big and small all factors account received without whole personality formation for uses.

References:

1. Begmatov E., Mamatov A. Literary norm theory . (Literary of the norm types) Part 2. - Tashkent , 1998. - B. 9-10.
2. Begmatov E. and etc. Literary norm and speech culture - Tashkent : Science, 1983. - B. 19.
3. Golovin B.N. Vvedenie v zazykoznanie . - M., 1977. - S. 234-235 .
4. Coulthard M. and Johnson A. Introduction to forensic linguistics. Book. - New York: Routledge, 2007. - P. 250.
5. Jorayev TT, Halimov SG'. Speech culture - Samarkand, 2021. - B. 39 .
6. Iskandarova Sh. Communication forms of Uzbek speech habit: Philology. science. name ... diss. autoref. - Samarkand, 1993. - 27 p.
7. Mamatov A.E. Problems of lexical and phraseological norms in modern Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent, 1991. - B. 39.
8. Ojegov S.I., Shvedova N.Yu. Tolkovyy slovar Russian yazykyu <http://ozhegov.info/slovar/>
9. Ojegov S.I. O normax slovoupotreblenia. Lexicology. Lexicography. Culture. - M., 1974. - S. 285-291
10. P urdy DC Identification of handwriting. In: Scientific Examination of Questioned Documents . 2nd ed. JS Kelly and BS Lindblom, Eds. CRC Press-Taylor & Francis, Boca Raton, Florida, 2006, p. 47-74.
11. Rorschach H. Psychodiagnostics; a diagnostic test based on perception: including Rorschach's paper, The application of the form interpretation test (published posthumously by Dr. Emil Oberholzer). Grune & Stratton Inc. , New York (1942). - R. 15.